

ACOUSTIC EMISSION ANALYSIS FOR VALIDATION OF MICRO MECHANICAL MODELS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, acoustic emission (AE) monitoring during tension tests is performed to investigate the failure behaviour of AS4/8552. Also, the validation of finite element micromechanical predictions is done by comparing with test results. Acoustic emission registration during test provides useful information about the type of damage accumulating during testing. Peak frequency analysis is used to classify the damage modes. For this purpose, first of all, pure resin materials are tested to determine the peak frequency value for matrix cracking. Secondly, one fibre bundle embedded in epoxy specimens are tested to compare the difference between pure epoxy in terms of AE behaviour. Thirdly, uncured carbon fibre reinforced thermosetting prepregs are tested to discriminate the AE behaviour of fibres and also prepregs from pure epoxy. After all, consolidated unidirectional (UD) and cross-ply (XP) carbon fibre reinforced thermosetting composites are tested in fibre and transverse directions. Epoxy material considered in this study is Araldite LY 5052® with its hardener Aradur 5052®. Prepreg composites are AS4/8552 and the number of plies for each specimen is limited to 4 plies for this study. Results of UD and XP configurations are compared with predictions of finite element micromechanical models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites materials generally consist of two constituents for their specific purposes. Their properties are function of these constituents. For fibre reinforced composites, fibres sustain the composite against the applied load, where the load transfer across the material is done by the matrix phase. This combination is very popular especially for their high strength-to-weight ratio. Therefore they are highly preferred in aerospace and transportation industry. However their mechanical behaviour is much more complex than conventional materials. Under an applied load there can exist fibre and matrix failures. In addition to this, relationship between them can cause different failure mechanisms such as debonding and even delamination. Nevertheless, if damage initiates in a composite structure, its stiffness degrades and its life decreases quickly. Therefore each damage mode in a structure should be identified during service and precautions should be taken. Non-destructive test (NDT) methods are of great assistance when working with laminated composites and they are used to determine the time and type of damage during an application. There are various types of NDT methods available. In this study only Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring is used. AE has been a popular method for the last 25-30 years for composite materials. Various studies have been performed to discriminate each failure modes. De Groot et. al [1] investigated the failure behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) under tension tests. Different configurations were used to match each frequency value to various types of damage. Thus, frequency ranges were decided for matrix cracking, debonding, fibre pull-out and fibre failure. Ramirez-Jimenez [2] investigated the AE behaviour of glass/polypropylene thermoplastic materials under tensile loading. They tested unidirectional (UD) and crossply (XP) laminates with 8 plies in 0°-45° and 90° directions. AE results were supported with SEM observations. So, the frequency ranges for each damage type were decided but some frequency ranges were left undecided and some failure modes were put in the same frequency range since they

couldn't be discriminated from each other. Gutkin et. al [3] investigated IM7/8552 composite under various types of loading with AE monitoring. Pattern recognition analysis was applied to AE signals with k-means algorithm, Self Organising Map (SOM) combined with k-means algorithm and Competitive Neural Network (CNN) for clustering. Secondly, AE signals were classified with respect to frequency contents of the signals. Chosen clustering algorithm was compared with classification according to frequency values and it was seen that both classification methods were very close to each other and frequency contents gave a reliable idea about failure modes. Lomov et. al [4] developed an experimental methodology and used it in many studies [4-10] for Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) composites. They considered the points where a sharp increase occurred at cumulative AE energy curves during the tests and mentioned these points as the "knee" points of the tests in which the slope of stress-strain diagram started to decrease. After several tests they cut the specimens and investigated the damage under optical microscope and concluded about the type of damage after knee points [4-7]. Then by using the frequency ranges obtained by Gutkin in [3], they tried to determine the failure modes for NCF composites [8]. The composite in [3] was a prepreg composite however they investigated NCF in [8] and the results obtained for prepregs composites were not effective for NCF. In [9] Li et. al. applied clustering method to AE signals and classified for failure modes in NCF again. The main parameters for clustering algorithm were chosen to be peak frequency and secondly amplitude with k-means algorithm. The validation of failure modes were done by comparing each signal types. In their final study, Li et. al [10] added in-situ observation of crack paths. Instead of a comparison between the signals of each cluster, the correlation between optical observation of crack initiation and progression with AE event recording was obtained.

These studies consider the failure modes with respect to different clustering methods. The main and the most distinguishing parameter was seen to be peak frequencies. Therefore in this study peak frequency values are chosen for clustering failure modes. On the other hand, according to authors' knowledge, there has not been a study that compared the results of AE monitoring and predictions by Finite Element Micromechanical Models (FEMM) yet. In FEMM, the relationship between the constituents and damage modes can be seen. It provides a good prediction in terms of strength however damage progression has not been validated yet. Comparing the predictions of damage evolution in FEMM with AE results is a good method for investigating micro failure modes since each AE signal has useful information about the type of damage accumulating during testing.

This is a preliminary study to make a comparison between macro and micro failure modes determined by AE monitoring and predictions by FEMM in terms of stress-strain response and damage progression. For this purpose, first of all, pure resin materials are tested to determine the peak frequency value for matrix cracking. Secondly, one fibre bundle embedded in epoxy specimens are tested to compare the difference between pure epoxy in terms of AE behaviour. Thirdly, uncured carbon fibre reinforced thermosetting prepregs are tested to discriminate the AE behaviour of fibres and also prepregs from pure epoxy. After all, consolidated unidirectional (UD) and cross-ply (XP) carbon fibre reinforced thermosetting composites are tested in fibre (0°) and transverse (90°) directions. Epoxy material considered in this study is Araldite LY 5052® with its hardener Aradur 5052® [11]. Prepreg composites tested are AS4/8552 and the number of plies for each specimen is limited to 4 plies. They are manufactured in autoclave by following Manufacturer's Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC) [12]. Test results of UD and XP configurations are compared to FEMM predictions given in [13-14]

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Specimen Preparation

Pure epoxy resin materials are produced from Araldite® LY 5052 epoxy resin with its hardener Aradur® 5052 [11]. Epoxy is mixed with hardener with a ratio is 40% of epoxy in terms of weight. They are mixed together and then simply poured into the silicon mold cavity. They are dog-bone specimens. They are cured for one day at room temperature and then end tabs are bonded to the parts. End tabs are glass fibre reinforced epoxy composites that have $[0/-45/+45/90]_s$ configuration used in every specimen. Secondly, single or a bundle of glass fibre (GF) and carbon fibre (CF) embedded

epoxy specimens are prepared with same method. The only difference is the fibres placed in the middle of the specimens.

Uncured prepregs are prepared from a single lamina. UD and XP AS4/8552 composite plates with 4 plies are manufactured with dimension of 270x400 mm. Each ply has 0.184 mm thickness according to the data sheet [12]. XP specimens have [0/90]_s and [90/0]_s configurations. Specimens in 0° and 90° directions are cut by a diamond blade with water cooling system. Then the edges are grinded for dimensional stability through the specimens.

2.2 Test Apparatus & Method

Instron® 8801 machine with 100 kN load capacity is used for tension tests. Extension during test is measured with Instron's non-contacting Advanced Video Extensometer (AVE). As mentioned above, ISO D-527 and ASTM D 3039-08 test standards are used for tension tests of pure epoxy and AS4/8552 specimens respectively. Test speed is chosen to be 2 mm/min.

USB AE Node System with PAC Software of MISTRAS Group [17] is used to monitor AE signals during tests. Piezoelectric sensors are PK 15I with operating frequency range 150-450 kHz. A threshold level of 50 dB is adjusted to eliminate noise from outside. Peak Definition Time (PDT), Hit Definition Time (HDT) and Hit Lockout Time (HLT) values are adjusted to 50-100-300 respectively as recommended in [17]. All signals coming from the transducers are recorded as hit data. Acoustic emission system produces signals which are characterized by seven AE features; Amplitude, rise time, counts, duration, energy, absolute energy, signal strength. In addition to these features, the most important AE parameter is peak frequency as seen in literature. The frequency of a signal provides important information about failure mode of the material. However peak frequency content of each hit could not be obtained easily with these 7 features in PAC software. A post-process is required to obtain peak frequency values for each hit. Waveform files of each hit are saved. These files contain amplitude (mV) and time (µs) of hits. An FFT transformation is required to collect peak frequency values of each hit. The number of hits reaches to 4000-5000 especially for XP laminates. So a MATLAB code is written to make FFT transformation and collect peak frequency values of each hit at one time.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MICROMECHANICAL MODEL

Details of the FEMM can be found in [13-14] but in this section, brief information about the models is given. Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) used in this study are shown in Figure 1 where yellow and blue sections represent fibres and resin respectively. Highlighted sections show the simplified models which provide symmetric and periodic results. In order to reduce time and computational cost, those parts are taken into account only. Tension tests are applied by considering two different conditions. The effect of process-induced residual stress is taken into account. Process-induced residual stresses developing in AS4/8552 throughout the MRCC is simulated by implementing a Cure Hardening Instantaneous Linear Elastic (CHILE) constitutive behaviour model. CHILE takes into account cure shrinkage strains as well as modulus development of the resin throughout MRCC. Variation of elastic moduli and strain of 8552 resin throughout cure cycle can be seen in Figure 2. It is not possible to simulate this behaviour by using available tools in ABAQUS® graphical user interface (GUI). So, instantaneous strain and temperature dependent elastic moduli of 8552 resin, are implemented into the user-defined subroutine, UMAT, to calculate the developing mechanical properties, generation of residual stresses and strain variation of AS4/8552 throughout MRCC. Progressive damage analysis is applied to assess the failure mechanism of AS4/8552 under tensile load modes. AS4 fibre is assumed to have brittle behaviour and only Maximum principal stress failure criterion is applied. The fibre failure occurs when the Maximum principal stress reaches the failure strength of fibre which is 4150 MPa as given in the data sheet [12]. Resin is also assumed to have linear-elastic and brittle behaviour in this study. One of the reasons is because in its technical data sheet, only one strength value is stated and it is not known when material begins to yield or fail. Tensile strength (σ_R^T) of 8552 resin is given as 121 MPa but the compressive strength (σ_R^C) is not available. In this paper σ_R^C is assumed to be 270 MPa. This assumption is based on back-calculation for transverse compressive loading with trial-and-error method by comparing with compressive

strength given in [12]. Various values are tried for transverse compressive loading and the most appropriate predictions are obtained when $\sigma_R^C=270$ MPa. 2 failure criteria are used in this study. Maximum Principal and Bauwen's MvM failure criteria. Stiffness degradation rule in progressive failure analysis is applied in USDFLD subroutine of ABAQUS® with these failure criteria.

Figure 1: Representative Volume Elements

Figure 2: Variation of strain and elastic modulus throughout MRCC.

4 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Tension Tests with AE Monitoring

Tension test results of pure epoxy specimen are given in Figure 3.a. The strength of 4th specimen is much lower than the rest. However, aside from 4th specimen, the average of strength for Arelidite LY 5052 epoxy specimen is 68.7 MPa with standard deviation of 5.27 MPa. Even though strength values vary a bit, results of AE registration is consistent for each specimen. So only 2nd specimen is presented in Figure 3.b. Very few hits are recorded during each tests and from all these tests only 2 different frequency ranges are observed. These are 130-160 (namely 131, 136, 141, 146, 151 and 156 kHz) and 20-60 kHz. The former one occurred before fracture but the later one occurred during fracture. So one can say that, both of them represent matrix cracking but former one is observed during fracture, namely it represents gross matrix failure. Some of failed specimens can be seen in figure 4.

Figure 3: Test results for pure epoxy specimens.

Figure 4: Failed pure epoxy specimens.

Secondly single or a bundle of GF and CF embedded epoxy specimens are tested and their results can be seen in Figure 5 and 6. In these tests a new frequency range is observed. That is between 220-260 kHz. Also, not given in Figure 5 and 6, but one specimen from each type gave one hit at 365 kHz and 400 kHz. The observed density of former range is higher than later one. Thus, it can be said that 230-260 kHz frequency range corresponds to fibre/matrix debonding. Because, there is no chance for any other failure to occur in single fibre embedded epoxy specimen under tension test. The possible mechanisms are matrix cracking, fibre/matrix debonding and fibre failure and since the density of 230-260 kHz frequency range is spreaded to the late portions of the test rather than a very small time gap as seen in Figures 5-6, this range is said to be fibre/matrix debonding. So, the frequency values 366 and 400 kHz which occurred at the end of the tests done on each specimen type shows fibre failure. The reason for not-observing these very high frequency values in each test can be due to condition of fibres in epoxy. Because, single fibres are laid by hand in the middle of the mold stretched by hand and taped from ends to provide a pre-load as much as possible, then epoxy is poured onto it. So maybe while some fibres are preloaded with this method some may not, so at the ones those preloaded fibre failure can be observed. Some failed specimens can be seen in figure 7.

Figure 5: Test results for GF embedded epoxy specimens.

Figure 6: Test results for CF embedded epoxy specimens.

Figure 7: Failed CF & GF embedded specimens.

Peak frequency values for matrix failure, debonding and fibre failure has been determined with pure epoxy specimens, but still different tests are required for fibre failure. Uncured AS4/8552 prepregs are tested. Their AE results are presented in Figure 8. Only 2 specimens are presented in Figure 8 for the sake of brevity. The most dominant failure mode is debonding and it can be easily seen with eye in Figure 9. So, high density of the frequency range between 230-260 kHz proves this. Aside from 20-60 kHz and 130-160 kHz there are 2 different ranges observed. First one is the range the frequencies greater than 290 kHz. The second is between 180-220 kHz. Frequency values greater than 290 kHz are believed to be fibre failure. Very high frequency values were recorded in CF, GF embedded epoxy specimens. However frequency values in this uncured prepregs test are generally 292, 312, 366 and 458 kHz. So comparison between single fibre embedded epoxy tests and uncured prepreg tests can give the difference between fibre failure and fibre pull-out. It is seen in CF, GF embedded epoxy tests, the specimen was fractured and captured AE signals were 366 and 450 kHz. So while these highest frequency values can correspond to fibre failure, frequency range between 280-320 kHz can represent fibre pull-out. But a deeper investigation is required for this part. Failed uncured specimens can be seen in figure 9.

Figure 8: Accumulation of AE signals with time in terms of peak frequency values.

Figure 9: Failed uncured specimens.

After the tests of all these “not completely composite materials”, frequency classification is about to be completed. Only the frequency range between 180-220 kHz is going to be determined. Now it is time to test consolidated composite materials. First of all, tension tests of UD AS4/8552 in 90° direction are performed. Results can be seen in Figure 10. For AS4/8552 results, only one specimen is going to be presented. The brittle behavior of AS4/8552 in transverse direction can be seen in Figure 10. Frequency levels determined above can be seen in Figure 10. So, few debonding occurs in the specimen, then frequency range between 180-220 kHz appears after 25 MPa, then at the end matrix micro cracking and gross matrix failure can be seen with frequency ranges between 156 kHz and 29 kHz respectively. Also, sharp increase in energy which is highlighted is the sign for considerable damage evolution. Cluster of frequency band at 185 kHz begins from this point.

Figure 10: Test result of UD AS4/8552 in 90° direction.

Test result for an AS4/8552 in 0° direction can be seen in in Figure 11. Considerable damage initiates around 1000 MPa. Also, some tests show that the average of damage initiation stress is 1093 MPa with a standard deviation of 125 MPa. The dominant frequency content is between 230-260 kHz which corresponds to fibre/matrix debonding. Then frequency band between 180-220 kHz is activated and finally matrix cracking occurs where micro matrix cracking is followed by fracture. One important result obtained from Figure 11 is that, just before final failure high frequency values are observed. Frequency values greater than 350 kHz and around 300 kHz are fibre failure and fibre pull-out respectively. One important unanswered question is that frequency band between 180-220 kHz. For now, it is thought to be delamination. Because until now the damage classification sequence with respect to frequency content is almost consistent with [3]. So it is thought to be delamination for this reason. However it appeared in uncured prepreg and the reason is not known yet. It is also important to note that the difference in energy values of uncured prepreg and AS4/8552 laminate in 0° direction. While around 6300 hits are recorded for uncured prepreg, only 235 hits are registered when testing the laminate. Also, the energy values are much lower in uncured prepreg than the laminate through the tests as shown in Figure 12. Energy levels are increased considerably through the end of the test for the laminate and final failure occurred with maximum AE Energy level observed through the test of

the laminate.

Figure 11: Test result of UD AS4/8552 in 0° direction.

Figure 12. AE energy of hits recorded during testing of AS4/8552 a. uncured prepreg b. laminate in 0°

Tension test results for AS4/8552 XP specimens are shown in Figures 13-14. These figures show the similar stress-strain response for both XP configurations. There is no sharp increase in cumulative AE energy curve. It is because, when damage initiates, hits with very high energy are recorded and the energy levels of next coming hits are high and close to first hits. So, more AE hits are recorded in XPs than UDs and their energy levels are also higher than UDs. In these figures two points are highlighted with grey and red straight dashed lines. Those lines show the initiation level of frequency clusters and high energy levels respectively. For [0/90]_s laminate, average of damage initiation level is around 400 MPa with a standard deviation of 45 MPa and for [90/0]_s laminate, that value is around 294 MPa with standard deviation of 62 MPa. These stress levels represent the initiation of micro-failures within the laminate. 4 different failure mechanisms are activated. They are gross matrix failure (20-60 kHz), micro matrix failure (130-160 kHz), delamination (180-220 kHz) and debonding (230-260 kHz). Detection of first high AE energy level increases to 465 MPa with a standard deviation of 29 MPa for [0/90]_s and 385 MPa with a standard deviation of 92 MPa for [90/0]_s. Reason of high standard deviation for [90/0]_s lamination is low number of tests has been conducted for now. Only 3 tests could have been done for them. Failed XP specimens can be seen in Figure 15. High amount of delaminations occurred on these specimens can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 13: Tension test result of [0/90]_s AS4/8552.

Figure 14: Tension test result of [90/0]_s AS4/8552.

Figure 15: Failed XP specimens a. [0/90]_s b. [90/0]_s.

According to the tests performed here, failure mechanism within 4 plied UD and XP laminates of AS4/8552 is thought to be understood. At least 2 different failure mechanisms are activated under loading in each perpendicular directions. Also, frequency patterns for each failure modes are determined. They are given in Table 1.

20 < F < 60	130 < F < 160	180 < F < 220	230 < F < 260	280 < F < 320	320 < F
Gross matrix failure	Micro matrix failure	Delamination	Fibre/matrix debonding	Fibre pull-out	Fibre failure

Table 1: Frequency content for failure modes obtained in this study

4.2 Comparison with finite element micromechanical prediction

Finite element micromechanical predictions for progressive failure analysis of UD and XP AS4/8552 were given in [13-14]. Briefly results are given in Table 2. As mentioned in [13-14] predictions with the effect of residual stress were closer to the test results available in literature. Therefore, while making comparison, only the results with the effect of residual stresses are considered. Damage initiation stress and final strength levels obtained from tension tests can be seen in Table 3. It is seen from 90° direction test results of UD laminates that, strength values are much lower than available value in data sheet [12]. It is also much lower than FEMM predictions as can be seen from Tables 2-3. The reason is that, the strength values for 8552 resin in [12] are used for modelling. So maybe those values in data sheet cannot be really true. For loading in 0° direction, damage initiation stress levels are close to each other however final strength predictions are over-predicted again. Addition to the reason mentioned here, another reason could be due to very small air voids trapped in laminates during manufacturing. Therefore these imperfections can cause lower final strength and strain during testing. But even the difference in final strength under 0° direction is less than 5%. There is no first ply failure under loading in 90° direction, but debonding and matrix cracking begins near the end of the test as shown in figure 10. For loading in 0° direction, it was mentioned above that damage initiation occurs around 1093 MPa. As shown in Table 2, damage initiation is observed at 1438 and 1070 MPa with respect to Maximum Principal and Bauwen's MvM failure criteria. So, Bauwen's MvM is not a bad prediction.

For XP laminates, difference between final strength values of FEMM predictions and test results is around 10%. Damage initiation levels are obtained around 400 MPa and 294 MPa with [0/90]s and [90/0]s laminates respectively. The predicted value with maximum principal failure criterion is 200 MPa. This can be considered as a close value for [90/0]s laminate. However, if there were more tests conducted the average of damage initiation stress level would be lower and the standard deviation would be lower than found in this study. More tests will be done until the conference date (19.07.2015) and more reliable results are going to be presented for [90/0]s laminate.

Prediction of damage progression with respect to maximum principal failure criterion for each type of laminates are given in Figures 16-18. Fibre failure in 0° is not shown. In Figures 16-18 red paths represent damage at given strain levels. Damage pattern predictions in Figures 16-18 are consistent with AE recordings given in Figures 10-14. So this preliminary study is an important step for the verification of FEMM with real mechanical behaviour of materials.

FEMM		With Residual Stress		Without Residual Stress			
	Resin Criterion	Damage Initiation	Final Failure	Damage Initiation	Final Failure		
UD	90°	Max. Principal	-	84	-	102	[MPa]
		Bauwen	-	42	-	93	
	0°	Max. Principal	1438	2388	-	2424	
		Bauwen	1070	2385	-	2424	
XP	Max. Principal	200	1172	610	1137		
	Bauwen	95	1174	648	1153		

Table 2: FEMM predictions for strength of AS4/8552.

TEST RESULTS		Damage Initiation		Final Failure		
		\bar{x}	σ_x	\bar{x}	σ_x	
UD	90°	-	-	41	9	[MPa]
	0°	1093	125	2136	152	
XP	[0/90]s	400	45	995	119	
	[90/0]s	294	62	1076	240	

Table 3: Test Results of AS4/8552.

Figure 16: Damage progression under loading UD model in 90° direction.

Figure 17: Damage progression under loading UD model in 0° direction.

Figure 18: Damage progression under loading XP model.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper is a preliminary study about validation of FEMM with tension tests by using AE monitoring method. Firstly, pure epoxy, single CF and GF embedded epoxy and uncured prepreps are tested with AE monitoring. Their frequency contents are investigated and classified for each failure mode. Then UD and XP AS4/8552 laminates with 4 plies are tested and failure mechanisms activated during testing are determined with AE recording. Then test results are compared with FEMM developed by authors in [13-14]. Damage initiation and final strength values are compared and relatively good agreement is obtained. However, there are some unrealistic predictions in FEMM. So for a better correlation, model should be developed. For example instead of using a predicted compression strength value for resin, which is calculated with back-calculation method by comparing with data sheet, a more realistic experimental value should be determined and implemented into the model. Also, resin can be considered as elasto-plastic material.

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